

SIGNIFICANCE OF LEARNER SUPPORT SERVICES IN DELIVERING HOLISTIC QUALITY EDUCATION IN LEARNING INSTITUTIONS IN KENYA

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Abstract:

This paper reviews literature on learner support services provided by learning institutions with a view to making recommendations on how the institutions could establish structures to support students' learning in order to provide them with the tools they need to be successful in the dynamic 21st century industry. Students' long term success is pegged on how well they are prepared with essential skills for life and the workplace such as leadership, communication, self-awareness into their own strengths and weaknesses, initiative, problem-solving, innovation and critical thinking. Training these skills requires learning institutions to provide learners with support services to enhance their learning. This entails putting in place programmes and co-curricular activities that engage learners in meaningful non-formal and informal learning and emphasizing experiential learning including community service, volunteer school activities and other core-curricular activities that enhance the development of the skills outlined above. Further, the institutions should enhance the development of more socially-conscious learners with positive values and attitudes that enhance good global citizenship. They should also provide them with coaching and mentorship programmes to help them discover their interests; develop self-motivation, innovativeness and excellence in performance. It is the author's hope that this paper will sensitize learning institutions to establish robust learner support services to enhance formal learning and also expose learners to experiences that equip them with skills for the 21st century industry.

Keywords: holistic quality education, learner/student support services, soft skills, personal and professional development

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1. Introduction

The economic and social benefits associated with education have influenced great competition in education that has in turn influenced teachers, students and parents in Kenya to focus more on examination and certification than education itself. This has over the years confined education in to knowledge transmission to passive learners whose role is simply to receive information from the unquestionable source and authority, the teacher through lecture. The students are then expected to give back the information they receive through tests and examinations where teachers require them to demonstrate that they received the knowledge transmitted to them by answering questions correctly. Freire (2006) describes this practice in education as a banking industry where teachers bank knowledge in learners and expect them to reproduce it back to them at an appointed time in the course of the term/semester. The practice has confined education to cognitive development and neglected the other aspects of education that make a whole person namely affective, psychomotor and social development.

Notably, the high premium given to examination and certification has influenced a stiff competition for the limited opportunities for jobs and access to higher education. This has compromised education so much that students, teachers and parents indulge in all kinds of examination malpractices including cheating in examination, buying certificates from the streets and impersonation of candidates in national examinations in an effort to help the candidate excel with the best mark in order to qualify to grab the available opportunities. The situation has over the years contributed to curriculum backwash as teachers continue to emphasize teaching sampled topics from the syllabus which are considered useful in effective preparation of students for national examinations while ignoring others. In effect, what students learn focuses on the knowledge and skills that are most relevant to the examination (Shiundu and Omulando, 1992). Such backwash effect is not conducive to holistic development of students' understanding of the disciplines they pursue (The Backwash Effect in Learning and Teaching, PolyU HKCC, & Biggs, 1995).

In addition, students do not benefit much from this practice of education because it offers them learning from the surface as they are not meaningfully involved in the activities of learning. Intervention measures are necessary if education in Kenya is to shift from the cognitive focus to a balanced approach that addresses all aspects of a complete person. A balanced education should develop learners in the cognitive, normative, creative and dialogical dimensions of education (Njoroge and Bennaars, 2000) in order to enhance their transformation as they go through the education process. Transformative education requires that what students learn in the classroom is enhanced through other avenues including student support services to provide them with an opportunity to develop soft skills through interaction with peers, mentors, coaches and academic advisors in informal set ups outside the formal classroom setting. This gives them the benefit of developing the personal and professional skills needed for success in the industry.

Student support services are the human aspects that support individual learners in their academic life and also provide a supportive learning environment. They include coaching and mentoring; student advisory services such as academic advising, guidance and counselling; sports and games; clubs and societies and financial services. Support services enable students to effectively concentrate in their learning as they are guided on courses to enroll for and advised on individual needs and challenges in order to enhance their academic life, making it more effective and comfortable (Glossary of Quality Assurance in Japanese Higher Education, 2007). The following section discusses mentoring and coaching, illustrating its significance in enhancing development of skills.

2. Mentoring and coaching

While the terms mentoring and coaching are often used interchangeably, they are very different disciplines in practice though similar in their support of someone's development. Mentoring is a long term relationship which focuses on supporting the growth and development of the mentee where the mentor is a source of wisdom, teaching, and support, but not someone who observes and advises on specific actions or behavioral changes in daily work. It includes training, support, encouragement, advice and guidance from people who have both done it before and are usually independent of the mentee's current organization.

On the other hand, coaching is a relationship of short term duration focused on strengthening or eliminating specific current behaviors such as helping professionals to correct behaviors that impede their performance or to strengthen those that support stronger performance around a set of activities (A Guide to Understanding the Role of a Mentor-The Balance, 2017). It is crucial that learning institutions work closely with the industry to ascertain that students are mentored by professionals in their field of specialization to equip them with relevant skills and competences demanded by the industry.

Mentoring has the benefit of supporting and encouraging students to manage their own learning to enable them maximize their potential, develop their skills, and improve their performance as well as become the person they want to be. It also enhances personal development and empowerment which helps people to progress in their careers. Mentorship aims at helping the mentees to find the right direction and to also develop solutions to career issues; providing them with an opportunity to think about career options and progress; helping them to boost confidence and belief in themselves; allowing them to explore new ideas and opportunities to help them become more self-aware in order to take responsibility for their life rather than leaving it to chance (What is mentoring?-Mentor SET). Providing learners with support services that can help them realize these aims is crucial in enhancing their holistic development as they go through the process of education.

Further, mentoring helps in developing specific skills and knowledge that enhances mentees' professional and personal growth from the mentor who facilitates them in various aspects including teaching about a specific issue, coaching a particular

skill, sharing resources and networks to facilitate growth, challenging the mentees to move beyond their comfort zone, creating a safe learning environment for taking risks and focusing on their total development (Definition of Mentoring-Benefits of Mentoring-Management Mentors). The mentor is expected to provide support to, and feedback on the individual in his or her charge (What is Mentoring? Definition and Meaning. Business Dictionary.com). However, to achieve success in mentoring, the mentor must become a role model to look up to, to emulate and to show one the tricks and pitfalls of the game.

Mentoring students has become critical today because the labour market is demanding graduates with a range of new competencies including those outlined above. This has made it imperative that learning institutions link with the industry to ensure that curriculum delivery enhances the development of the skills needed for the job market. To achieve this goal, learning institutions should invite professionals in the industry to facilitate the teaching of some topics and also organize some lessons/classes to take place in the industry, in order to give students a practical aspect of the theory they learn in class. Linkage should be emphasized because education stakeholders continue to express dissatisfaction on the quality of education offered in learning institutions and more specifically the quality of graduates being churned out by universities. Employers have expressed concerns that the graduates are lacking the key skills needed in the 21st century such as innovativeness, problem-solving, creativity and critical thinking (British Council, 2016).

World Bank (2015) for instance observed that graduates from Kenyan universities lack crucial knowledge, skills and competencies for the labour market. Scholars have attributed the low quality status of university education to the increased enrolments without commensurate funding, which has influenced the universities to operate with overstretched resources and facilities. Haphazard expansion without adequate staff and learning facilities is also a factor. The ripple effect of this status quo is that universities are overstretched financially to afford finances to invest in innovative programmes that can support students' learning. Consequently, they continue to churn out half-baked graduates (British Council, 2016). It is however, intriguing that this status quo continues to persist, yet the Commission for University Education Standards and Guidelines (2014) have outlined the need for learner support services in universities as prerequisites for enhancing quality learning. The situation further raises concerns on the effectiveness of the Commission for university education in quality assurance and standards as a regulator of university education in Kenya.

This notwithstanding, however, the commercialization of education and examination focus today casts doubts as to whether learning institutions consider learner support services as a priority where money should be spent. For instance, expansion of universities has led to offering education in the so called satellite campuses with makeshift classrooms with no ambience of a university. This has left students with only one option, to walk in and out of the makeshift classes, receive information from the lecturer and cram the notes when required to do a test or final examinations as most satellite campuses have no library. The student finally lines up to

receive a degree certificate after three or four years. This scenario has set many degree holders on the tarmac for years with degrees that cannot earn them a job because they were not offered mentorship and coaching on soft skills to enhance their employability. The Commission for University Education has tried to intervene by closing some campuses that fall short of the standard guidelines of establishing and offering university degree programmes although a lot more needs to be done.

3. Impact of Mentoring and Coaching

Research indicates that mentoring and coaching has an impact on both individuals and organizations. For instance, it helps individuals to increase reflectivity and clarity of thinking; improve psychological wellbeing and confidence; enhance better problem-solving skills including decision-making; enhance practitioner knowledge and skills; improve sharing of practice; achieve better communication and relationships; enhance more positive attitudes towards professional and career development, and improve self-management and self-learning skills.

On the other hand, mentoring and coaching helps organizations in the development of a culture of research and learning, reflection, collaboration, professionalism and recognition around professional and career development, high aspirations and vitality and pastoralism. Other benefits include enhanced personal effectiveness and ability to work smarter; development of techniques for constructively challenging unhelpful behaviours such as negativity and limiting beliefs; enhanced energy and job satisfaction; and increased personal productivity (The Impact of Mentoring and Coaching). The numerous individual and organizational benefits of mentoring and coaching demonstrate the need for learning institutions to establish structures that provide students with the support service in order to empower them with the skills they need to help them cope with the numerous challenges of today's dynamic society. Its benefit in enhancing increased personal productivity entails that mentoring and coaching has the potential to accelerate sustainable development.

However, success in mentoring requires mentorship programmes to establish student-mentor relationship by spelling out clear expectations and roles for both, including a written agreement between the student and the mentor, indicating the student's responsibilities and when they may need support from the mentor. Such an agreement allows students with disabilities to establish the assistance they need and also ensures that the mentor does not provide more help than is necessary. It further helps the mentor to see how to vary support, since every student's needs are different. Success is also achieved by establishing intensive individual and group mentoring and coaching activities and developing a school culture that fosters mentoring and coaching (Coaching and Mentoring: Supporting Students/ Think College).

3.1 Areas of Mentoring and Coaching

The areas include personal development, college access and persistence to graduation and acquiring skills critical to academic and career success (Coaching and Mentoring/

Pathways to College). Personal development is significant in increasing students' interest and participation as school leaders. This helps them to identify and seek leadership positions; establish eligibility and apply for honors awards and scholarships. It further helps them to engage with their peers to inspire and encourage academic excellence. Student-centered leadership should be preferred because it has the benefits of enhancing students' performance and motivation towards learning; improving teaching and learning practices and better behaviour including respect between adults and students (The Impact of Mentoring and Coaching). Involvement in student governments is also crucial in developing students with skills of citizenship such as integrity, patriotism and fairness. Learning institutions should establish student governments to enhance the development of the above skills. Interestingly, while universities in Kenya have basically embraced student governments, only a handful of primary and secondary schools have embraced it.

Supporting students in college access and persistence to graduation entails coaching them to explore career opportunities, seeking access to role models, being good mentees, serving as mentors to others, and reaching for competitive college admission when seeking their "personal best college." Effective coaching of students in these aspects has the potential of transforming them into empowered ethical citizens who are capable of promoting the spirit of community service as they engage in activities of serving their peers as mentors. Engagement in such activities is an added advantage to students because, as noted elsewhere in this paper, students who participate in activities beyond academics have better opportunities of securing a job compared to those who have nothing to show above the academic certificate.

Students should also be coached and mentored to acquire academic and career success skills including studying, goal setting and achievement; strategic thinking, writing, speaking and presentation skills; learning and research; and becoming well informed and aware global citizen (Coaching and Mentoring/Pathways to College). This helps them to focus on learning and the ultimate goal of education which aligns closely with career opportunities. Developing students with these skills is imperative as employers today are not just impressed by academic certificates; they are also keen to establish that an employee demonstrates possession of soft skills and ability to apply them. As such, learning institutions should establish programmes that can expose learners to forums that broaden their minds and develop their entrepreneurial and innovation skills. In this connection, institutions of higher learning should facilitate students with incubation hubs and innovation centers where professionals from the industry and university professors are invited to interact closely with students through public lectures, personal development, workshops and seminars or demonstration of a new plant in the market.

They should also facilitate students with diversified internships, halfway through the programme and towards the end to ensure that they get adequate practical experience of the world of work and apply the feedback from the industry experience to sharpen the skills needed for effective work performance. It would also help them to transition smoothly from school to the industry. This is crucial because as observed

above, there is a widespread concern about the work readiness of graduates because employers continue to lament on the mismatch in labour market demand and supply where universities are producing graduates lacking appropriate skills and knowledge needed in the workplace. Bridging this gap demands that learning institutions emphasize mentoring and coaching of students for the job market.

The following section briefly discusses academic guidance and advisory support.

3.2 Academic Guidance and Advisory

Academic guidance and advisory entails assigning a number of students to a teacher who assists them to make advancement towards their objectives and targets on individual basis. This enables individual students to exploit their potential according to their ability, interest and talent. It aims at helping students to make decisions regarding their career aspirations and to address the challenges they may face in their academic life. The academic adviser plays the roles of providing personalized insight and clarity into choosing classes; meeting academic milestones; helping students to position themselves for core-curricula activities and leadership; accessing students to the whole curriculum to help them to read ahead; discovering and helping to develop a student's interests through sharing of intriguing articles, inspiring developments, multimedia content, and discussion-based exploration; helping students develop social skills to build positive relationships with teachers, counselors, and outsiders-by teaching them the core elements of relationship building and how to stand out within a community; and teaching them stress management & social development-helping them build skills to surround themselves with good influences (Student Mentorship Programme/College Vine).

However, to play the outlined roles effectively, academic advisors should be empowered through adequate pre-service and in-service training to equip them with the knowledge and skills relevant to the roles. It also requires reforms in teacher training curricula to incorporate the skills in the curriculum in order to impart them to teacher trainees to empower them so that they become effective mentor and coaches to students. Reforms are particularly needed in Kenya because teacher training institutions are reported to be offering outdated curricula that are not in tandem with the needs of the society. Kafu (2015) for instance asserts that the inherited teacher education programme has not been adequately reformed to give it capacity to address issues of education in the African context in order to respond effectively to the emerging and evolving issues such as access to education by all, equality and equity in education.

Ochangi, Ayot, Kamina, Ondigi & Kimemia (2015) also report that there is a gap in the teacher education curriculum on the role of ICT in teacher education. The researchers observe that failure to integrate technology in teaching shows a mismatch between the education offered in schools and the needs of the society. This status of teacher education casts doubt as to whether teachers who have gone through the teacher training institutions can be effective academic advisors to students. There is urgent need to build teacher capacity through systematic teacher development

programmes to empower them with skills that enable them to effectively support students with academic guidance and advisory services as they go through the process of education.

Academic guidance and advisory should be emphasized for its benefits including enabling students to discover and develop new passions and interests which could inspire and motivate them to pursue ideas, interests, and hobbies; and potential to develop a student's self-motivation, passion, and leadership abilities. It could further establish a strong academic and core-curricula profile within a student's interests and also help students to keep on the right track, focusing on what is important to them. This can reduce stress and improve their overall wellbeing in school (Student Mentorship Programme/College Vine). Learning institutions should exploit the benefits of academic guidance and advisory outlined above to enhance holistic delivery of the curriculum.

3.3 Guidance and counselling

Guidance and counselling is a professional service aimed at assisting students to understand themselves, others, school environment and attain abilities to adjust accordingly (Gatua, 2012; Wango & Mungai, 2007). This service is crucial because students experience numerous challenges in school arising from the change of home environment to a new setting with new interactions and orientation and the surrounding community. The challenges, including social relationships, drugs and substance abuse may affect their learning if not attended. For instance, students who are not able to cope with the changes may resort to drugs and substance abuse, truancy and other undesirable activities that derail their focus on education. It is thus critical that learning institutions establish guidance and counselling structures to cater for students' social and emotional needs and to help them adjust to the school environment and also respond to emerging challenges in the society.

The structures should further expose students to different careers and professions from the early years of schooling to help them build their careers steadily as they go through the education process in upper primary and secondary school. They should also put in place peer counsellors to supplement the services offered by counsellors (Wango, 2007 & Gatua, 2012). Guidance and counselling benefits students in various ways including helping them to learn to set individual goals that enhance improvement of their academic performance; preparing them for unanticipated life events and ongoing personal difficulties and challenges faced in and out of the school. It also enhances the retention rates of students with high chances of dropping out (Cooper, 2007). Learning institutions should establish guidance and counselling structures in order to help students to go through their education smoothly and also develop them with soft skills such as self-efficacy and confidence.

Despite its significant benefits, Michubu, Nyerere & Kyalo (2017) report that availability of quality guidance and counselling service in universities in Kenya is low. Gudo, Olel and Oanda (2011) support the report noting that majority of the students (56%) in public universities are dissatisfied with guidance and counselling. The research

finding is paradoxical because the Association of University and College Counsellors survey (2002) cited by Michubu¹, Nyerere & Kyalo (2017) found out that all public universities in Kenya had established a guidance and counselling department in their campuses. This implies that universities have guidance and counselling departments in place but they do not offer quality services. Further, the research report is unexpected because Policy documents including Inter-University Council for East Africa (2010) and Commission for University Education Guidelines (2014) have outlined the need for learner support services in universities as prerequisites for creating quality environments to enhance quality learning. Providing vibrant guidance and counselling services in learning institutions should be emphasized because its benefits indicate that it is significant in enhancing holistic quality education.

In addition to the support services discussed above, students should be provided with sports and games, clubs and societies and financial support services to help them hone soft skills further for their personal and professional development. The following section briefly discusses the three services.

3.4 Sports and Games

Sports and Games play a significant part in the learner's school experience. A learner participating in school sports may have reduced anxiety and depression. He/she can also receive self-esteem boosts, which may improve confidence and school performance (Marianne Engle, 2013 cited in National Association for Sport and Physical Education, 2013). Development of self-esteem and confidence skills confirm the value of the support services in enhancing learning and developing learners with 21st century skills.

In addition, learners who play sports in school enjoy enhanced social interaction that could help them learn effective skills for interacting with both peers and adults and also enhance performance. Other benefits of sports and games include providing learners with a variety of character-building experiences such as how to cooperate with others and play fairly; enhancing development of learners' self-discipline as they strive to learn and excel at a sport, which could be transferred to academics and improve school performance; and enhancing critical-thinking and problem-solving skills (National Association for Sport and Physical Education, 2013).

Participation in sports also makes learners stay healthy and strong. It further increases endurance, builds healthy muscles and bones as well as controlling weight. Students who feel overwhelmed or tense with academic issues might benefit from involvement in sports activities. For instance, running releases negative anxiety and tension, and this enables students to concentrate in school. Physical benefits further impacts on learners' emotional well-being, which, in turn could improve school performance (The importance of Sports and Games in school, 2013). Learning institutions should exploit these benefits to enhance holistic development of learners as they go through the process of education.

However, to succeed in this endeavor, learning institutions should promote sports and games and require participation by every learner. They should plan activities for sports and games competitions among students within and outside the

institution. These suggestions notwithstanding, the high premium given to examination and certification has compromised students' participation in sports and games, particularly in upper primary and secondary classes. The schools use the time allotted to non-examinable subjects and school activities to cover the syllabus in order to prepare students for national examinations (Njui, 2010, Wamahiu, 2015).

It is the opinion of the author that reforms will change the education narrative in Kenya. Basic Education Reforms Framework (2017) for instance emphasizes sports and games in education and offers guidance on the need for schools to identify talented students in sports and guide them on the pathway to take as they advance towards higher education. The significance of sports and games is also well captured by the Commission for University Education Standards Guidelines (2014) which require all universities to ascertain they have adequate field facilities for engaging students in sports and games. To enforce this policy, the commission requires a university which does not have adequate fields for recreational activities to provide a written Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with an institution willing to lease its field facilities. A university is not licensed to operate without the memorandum. However, enforcement of this policy seems to be compromised, particularly in satellites campuses situated in towns with virtually no space for sports including in-door games. Students attending such campuses may never have an opportunity to participate in sports and games throughout their campus life.

3.5 Clubs and Societies

Clubs and societies offer students activities designed for fun, mutual trust and friendship among students, and enhance their experience beyond the classroom. They also provide an opportunity for them to meet other students who share common interests. Participation in clubs and societies helps students to develop their leadership skills as they get opportunities to organize and inspire peers as leaders of clubs and societies. This service strengthens opportunities for a student to access a job after graduation (Clubs and organizations/Mercyhurst University).

Further, clubs and societies enhance development of soft skills such as discipline, sharing, respect; positive attitude towards life and people; teamwork; negotiation; acceptance of different kinds of people (culture, colour, ability and religion); empathy and fair play. Learning institutions should establish a variety of clubs and societies and emphasize student involvement in them in order to enhance their development of the skills above for their success in life and workplace.

However, while primary and secondary schools in Kenya provide learners with opportunities to join clubs and societies of their interest, the high premium given to examination and certification has influenced schools to use the time allotted student support activities to prepare students for national examinations as noted above. Emphasizing learner involvement in the support services discussed in this paper demands a paradigm shift in education from emphasis of cognitive development skills development. This is imperative if education in Kenya is to align with the 21st century standards based education.

3.6 Financial Support services

Finances are a key factor in sustaining students in learning institutions. On this reason, the government of Kenya has made a significant effort to offer free primary and secondary education to ensure that children from poor households access education. However, implementation of free education has faced many challenges including high rocketing student numbers which have overstretched facilities and resources in learning institutions, particularly public universities. This has led to unmanageable student-teacher ratios that have made individualization of teaching impossible. These and other challenges have negatively impacted the quality of education offered in learning institutions.

On the other hand, university education is not free although the government has subsidized it for students gaining access through the regular government subsidized programme. However, students from poor household families still have a challenge raising money to pay for admission and other services. On the other hand, Those who gain admission to the parallel programmes and private universities are required to pay exorbitantly to attain education. This has become a big burden as the poor households cannot afford to support education for their children in universities. It also means that access to university education has become a privilege for children from rich families. Gichui (2015) confirms this noting that with rising economic challenges in many developing countries, students struggle to survive in universities as most households struggle to finance education for their children. He further asserts that this situation has been made worse by the government reduction in financing education. For instance, cost sharing policy in financing higher education in Kenya entails that students have to pay a certain amount directly to the university in order to be enrolled.

This situation calls for intervention measures to raise finances for the education of students from poor households to help them focus on education without interruption. Innovative strategies for raising funds including work study programmes, bursaries, scholarship, benevolence funds, and soft loans could support such students to achieve their dreams in education. This would in turn enable them to participate in the economic development of the society and thus contribute to the attainment of sustainable development goals. Financial intervention is crucial because researchers including Gichui (2015) and Michubu, Nyerere & Kyalo (2017) report that financial management and advisory services are inadequate in universities in Kenya. The researchers further note that the situation impacts negatively on the quality of education as students spend a lot of time looking for alternative ways to raise money for their education at the expense of academic work.

4. Conclusion

Life in school should not be solely about academics. Learners need a respite from their tough study schedules to re-invigorate their energies for overall holistic development. They also need to be helped to cope with challenges affecting the youth in the society which often result to derailing them from their focus in education if not attended.

Student support services play a significant role in supplementing formal classroom learning through practice and application of what is covered in the lessons. Further, they provide opportunities to develop students with soft skills including leadership, teamwork, negotiation and citizenship skills as well as opportunities to socialize with peers in an informal setting. As such, providing students with learning support service implies transforming them into empowered ethical citizens who have what it takes to effectively participate in the holistic development of the society. Learning institutions should exploit the numerous benefits of student support services if they are to equip students with the personal and professional skills needed for success in life and employment. Achievement of holistic quality education cannot become a reality in learning institutions without adequate learner support services.

5. Recommendations

The study recommends the following:

5.1 Provide Student Support Services

Learning institutions should provide students with key learning support services including mentoring and coaching, academic guidance and advisory, guidance and counselling, sports and games, clubs and societies and financial support to enhance students' development of the soft skills relevant to the 21st century industry by:

A. Providing Support to Students with Disabilities

Ramps should be put in place to facilitate learners with physical disabilities, escape points in case of fire and assistive technology such as braille for the visually impaired learners to enable them access curriculum with ease.

B. Strengthening Academic Guidance and Advisory

Learning institutions should strengthen academic guidance and advisory services to guide students on career paths as well as help them to cope with the challenges they might be facing in their respective programmes. This could enhance their concentration in learning and also improve performance.

C. Diversify Guidance and Counselling Services

Guidance and counselling structures should incorporate peer counsellors to supplement the services offered by counsellors.

D. Enforce the policy on the minimum standards for playing ground/fields

All learning institutions should abide with the policy on providing sufficient field(s) for sports and games. In particular, the Commission for University Education should enforce the policy on the minimum standards required for play fields/ grounds to ascertain that universities provide students with opportunities to engage in sports and games.

E. Establish Structures for Financial Support to Needy Students

Learning institutions should come up with strategies for raising funds to off-load students from deprived families from the financial burden of spending their learning time looking for school fees. This can help them focus on learning and unleash their potential in education.

F. Provide Students with Coaching and Mentoring Services

Learning Institutions should put in place intensive individual and group mentoring and coaching activities to enhance students' success in school day to day life, academic achievement, career success and personal development.

5.2 Build Teacher Capacity

Teachers should be empowered through pre-service and in-service training to enable them offer effective academic advisory to students. Offering them in-service training on regular basis would help them keep abreast with current research developments in education and trends in technology. This could enhance their responsiveness to the emerging issues in the society and also improve their teaching practice.

5.3 Link Education to the Industry

Learning Institutions should involve stakeholders and professionals from the industry in curriculum development and implementation processes to ensure their programmes are market driven.

5.4 Establish a Placement Department

Institutions of higher learning should put in place a placement department and link it to the industry. The department should keep a comprehensive data base of the current market demands and also work closely with the industry to ensure a regular interaction between professionals and the university faculty, staff and students for the purpose of exchanging ideas on the skills needed by the industry. It should also establish a link with the industry to facilitate students with internships and employment opportunities.

5.5 Institutionalize Community Service

Community service should be a requirement at all levels of learning because such activities develop soft skills which could develop graduates who are socially consistent with positive values and attitudes that enhance global citizenship as well as opportunities in securing a job.

5.6 Diversify Internship

Tertiary institutions should diversify internship programmes to enhance sufficient practical experience halfway through the programme and towards the end to ensure that students apply the feedback from the industry experience to sharpen employability skills as well as help them transition smoothly from school to the industry.

5.7 Establish Incubation Hubs and Innovation Centers for Mentoring Students

Learning Institutions should create regular forums which invite professionals from the industry to interact with students through public lectures, career talks, workshops and seminars or demonstration of a new plant in the market. Professionals could engage students on topical areas including entrepreneurship, innovation hubs and incubation as a way of opening them up to different job opportunities and job creation strategies.

The forums should include sessions for student personal development where motivational speakers can mentor and coach them on how to raise their levels of confidence, self-esteem and self-efficacy in order to improve their opportunities for success in and out of school. Such forums could expose students to the current market trends and enlighten them on career prospects.

5.8 Establish Local and International Networks

Learning Institutions should network with reputable similar institutions locally and internationally for the purpose of benchmarking to enhance building centers of excellence and strengthen quality assurance for continuous improvement of the delivery of education. Global networks are helpful in establishing whether an institution is equipping students with the skills for the global economy. They can also help each country to participate in building a global learning network that can ensure that learning across the globe is adequately preparing learners with skills and competences that enable them to collaborate and resolve the numerous challenges facing the world today.

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